

Is the Big Bang an artifact?

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Abstract

This paper briefly investigates the possibility that the Big Bang is an artifact of current measurement and theoretical frameworks. This re-examination is necessary because distance, size, and mass must be reappraised on a fundamentally different basis. Additionally, the most distant visible celestial bodies are also the most massive, while the majority of smaller bodies at the same distance are not visible and are screened out of consideration. In this case, the observed redshift could be dominated by gravitational redshift, which does not imply a recessional velocity. These same objects could even have an approaching velocity, where the associated blueshift is overwhelmed by the redshift caused by the immense gravity of those largest visible bodies at ever-increasing distances. Consequently, the Hubble constant loses its purported meaning. Therefore, universe expansion and the Big Bang theory may be man-made artifacts.

1 Introduction

A thorough investigation of gravity and cosmology is underway in a separate working book (Danilatos, 2024). What began as a novel investigation of push gravity beyond the original ideas of Fatio (Wikipedia contributors, 2018b) and Le Sage (Wikipedia contributors, 2018a) in version 1 has gradually evolved to include many other fields of physics through to version 20. In essence, it is becoming a novel approach to cosmology within an alternative framework of New Physics.

This paper is an extract from that work, specifically concerning the expansion of the universe and the Big Bang theory. It appears we can provide a resolution to the many emerging problems of established theories on these matters. The use of the James Webb Space Telescope (JWST) has pushed these issues to a crisis point, which has encouraged us to present our position and query on these topics.

We begin with a novel understanding of the meaning of mass, which is necessary to describe celestial bodies like planets, stars, and neutron stars within a new physics framework. Astronomical and astrophysical parameters such as size, distance, luminosity, and velocity depend on what we have conventionally understood as mass. This alternative interpretation of mass necessitates a revision and reappraisal of the measured and accepted astronomical parameters, including the subject of this paper: universe expansion and the Big Bang.

While this is an initial qualitative presentation, quantitative support is now provided in a recent report entitled “A Gravitational Selection Bias as an Alternative to Cosmic Expansion: A Push Gravity Interpretation of the Redshift–Distance Relation” (Danilatos, 2025).

2 The meaning of mass

The meaning of “mass” has been a major key issue in physics since Newton. In fact, the word “mass” has been a misnomer that continues to fuel various problems across most fields of physics. For a long time, it has often been identified (or implied) with the amount of substance or matter in a physical body, hence the talk of “massive” bodies. Even the theory of relativity, with its mathematical conceptions of mass (like gravitational, intrinsic, and rest mass versus relativistic mass), has rendered the meaning of mass even more complex. Relativistic mass has been so confusing, even among notable figures in relativity, that it has been called “a pedagogical virus” by Okun (2006). We have attempted to relate relativistic mass to “real-mass,” whereby they differ only marginally, except as we approach velocities very close to the speed of

light (Danilatos, 2024). It appears scientists are hesitant to move away from it, which may be preventing further progress.

It seems the novel theory of push gravity (PG) has cut the Gordian Knot of “mass.” The concept of mass is “unveiled” in the brief description below.

Material bodies do contain an amount of substance, which we have chosen to term “hyle.” We avoid the term “matter” because there is also “antimatter,” whereas *hyle* incorporates both matter and antimatter. In the original development of PG, we used the alternative term “real-mass” for hyle, which continues to be used interchangeably in our cited main report.

We have further introduced the term “gravion” in reference to prior push corpuscles and to “gravitons” in existing theories because we wish to develop PG on a clean slate based on first principles, independent of related conceptions of “push particles” in other forms of pushing gravity. For simplicity, we start with a spherical material body containing an amount of real-mass m . Gravions interact with the sphere via a coefficient k , defined as the number of absorption events per unit length. If the real-density is ρ , then the ratio k/ρ is a universal constant Λ :

$$\Lambda = \frac{k}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

The symbol Λ is used in our development of PG (main work) and should not initially be confused with the same symbol used for the cosmological constant. The physical meaning of Λ is the number of gravion absorption events per unit surface-density (or mass-thickness) that take place inside a spherical body with real-density ρ , resulting in acceleration g at a distance r from the center of the sphere.

Omitting here all the detailed steps in PG derivations, we use J_0 for the universal density (intensity) of the gravion flux in free space as it applies at least over extensive regions of the universe. Gravions being absorbed by a given material sphere with radius R create a gravitational field around it with a resulting acceleration g_R at the surface of the sphere. With increasing real-density (or total real-mass), the acceleration increases monotonically and reaches a universal maximum (limiting) value g_0 . We provide the relationships among these quantities:

$$g_0 = \pi \frac{J_0}{c} \Lambda = \frac{\pi G}{\Lambda} = \frac{\pi \rho G}{k} \quad (2)$$

where c is the velocity of gravions and G is the familiar gravitational constant (Big- G) now worth writing also as

$$G = \frac{1}{\pi} g_0 \Lambda_{PG} = \frac{J_0}{c} \Lambda^2 \quad (3)$$

A novel quantity is the absorptivity A_R , which is a function of the product kR :

$$A_R = 1 - \frac{1}{2k^2 R^2} + \frac{\exp(-2kR) \cdot (2kR + 1)}{2k^2 R^2} \quad (4)$$

Then, the acceleration at distance r from the center of the sphere is provided by:

$$g = g_0 A_R \frac{R^2}{r^2} \quad \text{and} \quad g_R = g_0 A_R \quad (5)$$

Then, Newton’s gravitational law for the force F between two spheres with radii R_1 , R_2 and absorptivities A_{R_1} and A_{R_2} is replaced with:

$$F = \pi \frac{g_0}{\Lambda_{PG}} \frac{A_{R_1} R_1^2 A_{R_2} R_2^2}{r^2} = p A_{R_1} A_{R_2} \frac{\pi R_1^2 \pi R_2^2}{r^2} \quad (6)$$

where $p = J_0/c$ is a pressure exerted by the gravion flux. Neither the classical “mass”, nor the “universal” constant G appear any more. Instead, we have the cross sectional areas of the spheres and their absorptivities. It all boils down to the geometry of the system together with the interaction of gravions with material bodies via the coefficient k . The above law is derivable and is valid for all bodies Newtonian or not, for ordinary planets, stars, white dwarfs, neutron stars and black holes (see also Appendix). It is applicable inside entire regions of the universe of the order of the mean free paths of gravions. For regions greater than the mean free path, following a transition region, we finish up with a gravion gas governed by its own physics, analogous but not the same as ordinary gases. For those greater regions, there is a cosmic weather governing the celestial bodies embedded in it. It is likely that spiral galaxies correspond to terrestrial storm patterns. The latter could also explain the “anomalous” (unexpected) rotational speed of galaxies and much more.

Now, we have further found that the familiar gravitational mass is only a subset of the real-mass. This is the fraction of real-mass that interacts with gravions. It is only this fraction that is activated by the gravions

and is acted upon by gravitational forces. We have termed this fraction by “effective mass” and symbolized it by m_e . It is only this fraction that manifests classical “inertia”, which actually is also a misnomer. “Inertia” means inaction, the same as in other languages, e.g. in Greek inertia $\iff \alpha\delta\rho\acute{\alpha}\nu\epsilon\iota\alpha \iff$ inaction (inactivity). In physics, we have used the word “inertia” to describe our experience, when we try to change the kinetic state of a body. We experience a resistance to any change, but this is a reaction to our action. Reaction is action back upon us. The body is not acting inertly, so a more appropriate word might have been “reactivity” of the body, not “inertia”. In chemistry, the term is used correctly: It is more appropriate to call an inert element so, because the element does nothing by way of (chemical) reaction; it is action-neutral. However, in physics, all bodies are not action-neutral, when prompted to move, or stop, or change velocity. They all present reactivity and not “inertia”. This is not trivial semantics that we can overlook any more, it is a matter of properly understanding physical phenomena as we can now do via PG. Classical (conventional) “inertia” ultimately arises (originates) from the gravions, when we attempt to change the steady-state equilibrium of gravion interaction with a given material body, thus forcing a change in the established gravitational field associated with the given body.

The real-mass is initially inactive (inert) with reference to gravity, until it reacts with gravions, as inevitably all bodies do in the real world. Since only part of the body reacts with gravions, it is only this part that displays the classical “mass”, which we must now strictly call effective mass (instead of “inertial” mass). The remaining part of the real-mass is inactive, or passive, having no “inertia” per conventional definition of the term. Then we can readily write:

$$m_{passive} = m_{real} - m_{effective} \quad (7)$$

We have further coined the term “black” mass m_b , i.e. $m_b \equiv m_{black} \equiv m_{passive}$. This would be consistent with a description of the interior mass of black holes and would avoid confusion with the term “dark” matter already in use by existing physics terminology - but with a different meaning. Thus, we can concisely rewrite the above equation as:

$$m = m_e + m_b \quad (8)$$

We can go further: In lieu of the well established energy-mass equation $E = mc^2$, we have derived a more fundamental and more general equation in PG:

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = 4cg_0m_e \quad (9)$$

where $\frac{dE}{dt}$ is the rate (power) of energy absorption (via gravions) by a spherical material body. If the interaction time (or time constant) of gravions is t_g , we have also found that:

$$g_0 = \frac{c}{t_g} \quad (10)$$

and it follows that

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = 4\frac{c^2}{t_g}m_e \quad (11)$$

Then, we obtain for the effective mass:

$$m_e = \frac{\frac{dE}{dt}t_g}{4c^2} \quad (12)$$

It is found that $\frac{1}{4}$ of the absorbed energy associates with the effective mass, leaving only an effective energy E_e provided by the integral (with a fixed steady-state power absorption):

$$E_e = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{dE}{dt} \right)_{fixed} \int_0^{t_g} dt = \frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{dE}{dt} \right)_{fixed} t_g \equiv \frac{1}{4} \frac{dE}{dt} t_g \quad (13)$$

Finally, we obtain our PG equation for the effective mass:

$$m_e = \frac{E_e}{c^2} \quad (14)$$

The above equation is identical in form with $E = mc^2$, which, however, is only a subset of our PG derivation. Eq. 12 states that the mass of any body depends on the energy absorption rate (power) $\frac{dE}{dt}$ multiplied by the gravion interaction time t_g . We can better understand the significance of this important equation, if we start thinking about a macroscopic body like a planet. The energy absorption rate depends on the absorption coefficient k (the number of absorption events per unit length in the body). It is all those events that take place in time t_g , which add up to produce the numerator of the fraction in that equation. It is the synergy of concurrent absorption events adding up to produce an effective mass, the absorptivity and the associated acceleration g of the given planet. This understanding applies to any absorbing body, including a single photon, for which we have initiated a new study in the cited main work. The idea of synergy and concurrency applies all the way down to some minimum size structures of absorption and emission centers (MAC/MEC) first described by a 3+1 mass scheme.

The above is important, because the well known energy-mass equation does not involve or say anything about a coexisting or collateral hyle (black mass) in any given body. The hitherto conventional “mass” and “energy” have left out of consideration the bigger picture of the universe containing real-mass (hyle). The missing part of the universe, as interpreted by PG, could be a much better description than the missing “dark matter” and “dark energy” necessitated by established physics. Not only have we derived the famous $E = mc^2$, we have also found that it is only a partial case in physics. PG provides a greater framework to describe the cosmos, whereas prevailing theories describe only a subset of it. PG could become the New Physics to describe the universe and overcome the ever emerging impasses by prevailing theories.

We can finally see that classical “inertia” appears every time we attempt to change the characteristic fixed $\left(\frac{dE}{dt}\right)_{fixed}$ power exhibited by any given material body. This happens when we accelerate or decelerate the given body. “Inertia” is not some innate propensity for resistance by the body itself, but a resistance by the gravitational field to reconfigure with the body’s change of kinetic status.

3 Mass distribution in absorption layers

The effective (gravitational) mass is activated by the absorption of gravions and is distributed from the outer surface of a sphere towards its center with monotonically decreasing density. This variation is minimal for planets, and gradually increases with stars, white dwarfs, neutron stars and generally with increasing total real mass all the way up to black holes. A diagrammatic conceptualization of the gravitational mass variation is depicted in Fig. 1. In this way, the interior of massive (very dense) bodies is described by a completely different way from current physics.

We can say that there is some fraction of black matter even in ordinary objects. That fraction can be exceedingly small, moderate or excessive depending on the size and density of the object. There must be more of this stuff in the Sun than in the Earth. The amount of gray color-level showing in the diagrams in Fig. 1 gives some idea about it (not to scale). We may visualize more black matter towards the center of celestial bodies. In doing all this, it is important that we have only considered some average density throughout each of the above bodies, whereas in reality the density can be variable. We have found in the theory of PG that actual density distribution can alter all other parameters involved. The same applies for the planets and stars, so that the picture conveyed by Fig. 1 for the Sun could be misleading. Those workers who have all the relevant data about the Sun may like to see how we can build the correct PG picture of the Sun. The same applies for all other bodies in the figure, and not only. We have selected those four typical types of bodies, but all other intermediate bodies with all available data could be re-worked to fit, or to see if they can fit under PG.

The mass distribution layers depicted can be computed from the governing equations. We can assign an effective “thickness” to these layers for a sphere. We have introduced an effective *total absorption layer (TAL)* thickness to characterize each case. This is the thickness over which practically all incident gravions are absorbed yielding a maximum acceleration on the surface of the given body. Clearly, this does not happen in practice with all bodies depending on the relationship between the radius R and TAL for each case. For planets and stars, we expect that $TAL > R$, whilst for “heavy” celestial bodies we have $TAL < R$. In particular, for Newtonian bodies we have $TAL \gg R$. Ultimately, in black holes the effective mass is concentrated in a relatively thin outer layer with $TAL \ll R$ resembling the event horizon (Schwarzschild surface). See more on this in the main work by Danilatos (2024).

The above picture concerns initially the gravitational push particles, but we have also introduced corresponding push particles for the electric field and similarly for other force fields. A generalized push field theory is still under development, so that we omit the total effect of all possible types of push particles in order to minimize the size of this paper mainly aimed at the subject of the expansion of the universe.

Figure 1: Diagrammatic perception of the Sun (upper-left), white dwarf (upper-right), neutron star (lower-left) and black hole (lower-right) with their corresponding total absorption layer

The above is an initial conceptualization of what could happen around and inside stars and other massive bodies, but is subject to later modification as we develop and better understand PG theory. Even the proposed classification of various fields (electric, nuclear, etc.) and various types of push particles need proper adjustments along with corresponding fractions of effective and black mass, for example, when existing information on surface gravity of those bodies is revised.

In the above general scheme, we imply that the maximum value of a starting g_0 is sufficient to trigger the first transition of a star to a white dwarf. Depending on the literature source, the pressure at the center of the Sun may range between 3×10^{13} - 3.5×10^{16} Pa. This is expected to be well below the maximum pressure by gravions predicted and given by

$$p_{0g} = \frac{J_0}{c} = \frac{g_0^2}{\pi^2 G} \quad (15)$$

which will be known when J_0 or g_0 is finally measured. For a low tentative $g_0 = 4 \times 10^4$ m/s², we have $p_{0g} = (4 \times 10^4)^2 / (\pi^2 G) = 2.43 \times 10^{18}$ Pa. This pressure is consistent with existing requirements for a star on the main sequence to collapse to a white dwarf. The pressure at the core of Sirius B (white dwarf) is estimated to be $\times 10^6$ that of the sun, which means that we need a $g_{02} > 10^3 g_0$. In a later revision of PG theory, we have projected that g_0 should be $g_0 > 10^7$ m/s², hence there should be no difficulty with current astrophysical theories on the transition of stars to white dwarfs and so on.

If the conceptualization of various bodies in Fig. 1 is generally correct, it would question the validity of existing methods for finding their mass, radius and distance. There shouldn't be a serious problem for the main sequence stars, if their contraction factor q is not far from unity (see main Report). From the observed (intrinsic) brightness, color (temperature) and distance, the established measurements of mass and radius might involve only a small correction, but for stars outside the main sequence, in particular for white dwarfs etc, we may have significant discrepancies between existing values and reality. To address this problem, we would probably also need to develop a concurrent quantum theory of push gravity. We need to re-appraise conceptions and requirements of established theories of nuclear particles and force fields. We now see that PG opens new possibilities for modeling our physical observations. For example, the Chandrasekhar curve may need re-adjustment, if we note some discrepancy with PG, rather than discard or object to PG theory.

4 Are universe expansion and the Big Bang theory artifacts?

Based on the preceding analysis and further considerations below, universe expansion and the Big Bang theory are under question. The reasons of our query are presented in three groups:

(1) Because the methods for finding the mass, radius and distance of various celestial bodies require adjustments and corrections based on PG, a reappraisal of the Big Bang becomes necessary. The expansion of the universe is deduced from plotting the recessional velocity against distance, whereby the velocity is deduced from the redshift of distant bodies (Hubble's law). To the extent that redshift is based on photometric methods, which have already proved to be only an estimate by existing methods, PG adds additional reasons to further question the outcomes for the recession velocity of astronomical objects.

(2) The "tired light" theory has, by and large, been abandoned (it is said) as reason to reject the cosmological redshift. It has been questioned whether distortions of photons are created at the source or during their travel in space. However, until we can better determine the nature of photons with respect to their emission, transmission and absorption, tired light theory remains as a candidate for questioning the expansion of the universe. In this connection, PG is currently developing a new understanding of the nature of photons in the main report on PG (Danilatos, 2024). Lovyagin *et al.* (2022) have also challenged the tired light rejection and "*show that a static model can provide a natural and straightforward way of solving the puzzle*" as revealed by the JWST.

(3) However, there is an additional reason for questioning the Big Bang: After considering all possible causes of the redshift, the remaining gravitational redshift may play the main reason for abandoning the expansion theory. It may be that the most massive bodies at very long distance overwhelm all other determinations of redshift from visible data. It is only those massive bodies that can be (are) visible and detected, while all smaller bodies at the same distance are not detectable due to light loss in the intervening distance and space. If that is what happens, then the redshift (spectroscopic and/or photometric) does not represent the entire contents inside the given visible distance. These largest bodies can be moving away or closer in equal numbers, but their gravitational redshift overwhelms the Doppler shift (red or blue). Therefore, the redshift on average can be biased in favor of the dominating massive bodies providing a misleading impression about the average motion of all visible bodies. In that case, the redshift predominantly represents "size" towards the outer regions of the universe (if it is mainly due to gravitational shift). The farther the distance, the more gravitational redshift (than recessional redshift) is represented in our measurements. It

is said that gravitational redshift can take on a large range of values. Then size becomes very important, to an extent that overtakes the recessional redshift. In that case, we cannot claim that redshift (overall) of very distance objects represents velocity, but more so it represents size. By “size” we mean a combination of effective mass and real mass (per PG) together with radius, all of which relate to luminosity and distance. If the methods of measurement of mass, radius and distance require revision for all the reasons presented in the previous section and if light absorption during travel further complicates our measurements, then the redshift relationship to size and distance need to be reworked also. In that case, we would need to plot the size against distance, whereby the shape of the graph may not be linear any more (a shape to be found). In that case, the long established tenet of velocity versus distance relationship (Hubble’s law) should be revoked.

The high gravitational redshift originates not only from individual bodies inside a galaxy, like stars, dwarfs, neutron stars, black holes and so on, but also from collective action of all these components of a galaxy. The very distant galaxies may behave like a single body, collectively, as the photons travel through them and undergo successive gravitational redshifts, a kind of an effective overall redshift for the entire galaxy.

Added to that, some of these galaxies may be dusty enough to cause redshift (Naidu *et al.*, 2022; Kokorev *et al.*, 2023; Gottumukkala *et al.*, 2024; Giulietti *et al.*, 2024). That is, the interstellar medium inside a galaxy can also play a key role in redshift adding to the reasons we cited for negating the universe expansion. Tired light may still play an important role within galaxies, if not in the intergalactic space.

In any case, we propose that the universe is uniform in all directions with regards to average velocities and sizes of all celestial bodies, however, not all of which are visible within the maximum visible universe. There are (maybe) equal numbers of bodies with redshift and blueshift in all directions. We mean at sufficiently (very) long distances, because PG allows variations of physical constants (like G) from region to region sufficiently apart. However, the most (or more) distant ones that are visible happen to be also the biggest (or bigger), so that we inadvertently filter out the smaller ones during our observations. Our observations would then be biased and introduce an artifact by the outer visible galaxies in our thinking that they are moving faster than the closer ones. In that case, the Big Bang can be simply an artifact. It can be an artifact merely of the visible universe and not of the actual universe altogether, namely, observable and not observable (as defined by special relativity). Note: The “average” and “sufficient” words here have relative significance to be established by the actual data available in each referenced case.

5 Discussion and conclusions

All of the above require considerable amount of work on both existing and new astrophysical/astronomical data, before we can accept them as a denial of the long established universe expansion and “big bang” beliefs. All this could be clarified, when cosmologists reappraise and review their methods of measurement now to be based on the new framework of PG. It is said that measuring photometric redshift is easier to use than direct distance measurements, but this is not only a crude method, it can also be wrong on account that it is not known how luminous objects are in reality, especially in view of Fig. 1. The use of such means to measure the masses of objects independent of the mass-to-light ratio may contribute to artifacts (= errors in natural science, i.e. in the perception or representation of any information introduced by the involved equipment or technique(s)). These problems are convoluted by the new possibilities of reality revealed by PG as outlined in our main work.

If PG does indeed provide a new real framework for new physics and if astrophysical and astronomical measurements do indeed require a re-calibration, then not only the Big Bang theory based on observed universe expansion could be reconsidered as unreal, but also all other competing alternative theories may stand on shaky ground (re cosmic microwave background (CMB), steady state model, etc.).

It is said that “*CMB radiation is landmark evidence of the Big Bang theory for the origin of the universe.*” However, even this should also be reappraised. In particular, it is said that “*With a standard optical telescope, the background space between stars and galaxies is almost completely dark. However, a sufficiently sensitive radio telescope detects a faint background glow that is almost uniform and is not associated with any star, galaxy, or other object*” (Wikipedia contributors, 2024b). The spectroscopic measurements in the space between visible galaxies may not be an empty space filled with “background” radiation, after all, that is independent of the ever present cosmic bodies. The allegation (or assumption) that the CMB is the remnant of the Big Bang may prove to be entirely arbitrary and the ensuing support for the Big Bang unwarranted. In that intervening gap, there can actually be a practically infinite number of galaxies, of which only the most massive ones get their light through to us to see and measure. As we increase the angular resolution, our spectroscopic/photometric measurements in that “space” may simply resolve clusters of those most massive bodies, which at the same time appear “redder and redder shifted” on the micro-wavelength scale. The

remaining background (literally) radiation that is left between, say, the ultimately resolvable (by humans) bodies can be simply coming from the yet farther un-resolvable bodies of the universe. In that case, the CMB cannot be another confirmation of the Big Bang theory, it is only a true background radiation of a flat universe. Furthermore, the paradoxical discrepancy of the rate of expansion of the universe based on spectroscopic redshift and on CMB redshift (Hubble tension) might or might not be resolved, but this by itself does not solve the main problem. It is beyond the means available to this author to carry out such work, which is left to ambitious cosmologists to work it out. This author only projects his philosophical tenets in physics on this matter by use of the available resources to him: The space can easily be filled with a cosmic fluid (e.g. of gravions), and the space can be overall homogeneous and isotropic over sufficiently large scales. This is a sound philosophical basis to work with until proven otherwise.

If universe expansion and the Big Bang become redundant, a lot of complicated theories will be unnecessary and our understanding could be greatly simplified. The universe could be much simpler than we have thought so far. If we start with a wrong premise (like universe expansion), we are constrained to formulate needlessly complex mathematical relationships only to comply with the wrong starting point of our theories. For example, take “*proper and comoving coordinates*” introducing only redundant hard-and-complex work for cosmologists. We may have misconceived the nature of the universe due to systematic biases and errors (both experimental and theoretical). The universe can easily be static and always comoving. Philosophically, the universe in its eternity must not change to something else overall, but it always flows within itself. The Big Bang theory is philosophically untenable. The vacillations between contracting or expanding universe must have been in vain. We advocate the “static” and “flat” universe, to the requirements of which we should comply from now on, until we find unchallenged evidence for otherwise.

There is no need for the present author to delve deep into the long literature of the universe expansion and the Big Bang theory, since, especially following the launch and use of the JWST, a momentous debate has skyrocketed worldwide.

The “Hubble Tension” is a point of current controversy, and not only that. New contradictions expose a fundamental gap in the understanding of cosmos, so that “new physics” becomes necessary. We mentioned several reasons for that. A flaw also in the Lambda Cold Dark Matter model and Dark Energy driving the expansion of the universe are under question too (Riess *et al.*, 2024). Even if the Hubble Tension is somehow resolved, it is still signaling New Physics (Freedman, 2024), while the Big Bang theory can still be an artifact.

We are bombarded with expressions like “*The Universe Has Stopped Expanding! James Webb Space Telescope Shocks the Entire Space Industry!*” We hear that “*Galaxies appear small, smooth and surprisingly old in the JWST, but according to the big bang theory, as space expands, they should appear larger as they move away due to the stretching of light: However, the galaxies become smaller as the distance increases*”... “*Even galaxies with greater mass and brightness bigger than our galaxy appear in the JWST images 2-3 times smaller than the previous images obtained by the Hubble telescope*”... Also “*the redshift is 2-3 times greater challenging the assumptions of an expanding universe. They must be exceptionally tiny to explain the optical illusion (mighty mouse galaxies)*” (Labbe *et al.*, 2023)... “*The age of the universe appears to be older than previously thought, if to explain the new findings with galaxies as big as our own, even after a few million years after the big bang*”... “*The number of redshifted galaxies above 10 is 100000 times greater than predicted*”... and “*if verified with spectroscopy, the stellar mass density in massive galaxies would be much higher than anticipated from previous studies on the basis of rest-frame ultraviolet-selected samples*” (Labbe *et al.*, 2023)... All of these and much more are not expected by “established” theories and the expansion of the universe is now seriously questioned. We hope that our PG theory provides the ultimate framework to arrive at a much better understanding of the cosmos. The absence of any mention of our theory (PG) in what appears to be a long and comprehensive list of “*Alternatives to general relativity*” (Wikipedia contributors, 2024a) leaves much to be desired about the status of physics today.

The expansion of the universe and the Big Bang theory have further been questioned, for different reasons, by Postolak (2024) and Afanasev & Katanaev (2024).

5.1 Further notes and remarks.

It is understandable that the short presentation in this paper can raise many questions, some of fundamental importance. One question is what happens to the absorbed energy, which being so immense would melt the planet away in minutes. Another question is if the theory is at all compatible with the Second Law of Thermodynamics, plus what we say about the expected drag presumed to arise from the gravions. Furthermore, PG does not depend on the elsewhere assumed, now redundant, Equivalence Principle, of which the latest space test (STEP) by Touboul *et al.* (2019) has already been addressed: The reader is referred to the main cited report, where we think we have provided satisfactory answers.

That the mass and gravitational field are emergent properties (are the result) of the action by push particles has also been found by Fedosin (2015), who has followed an alternative approach to PG; along with several other reports, he has contributed towards the development of PG. Our approach differs in that we attempt to develop PG as a self-contained theory and framework on its own first principles without dependence on existing theories. Furthermore, we have clearly moved beyond Newtonian mechanics with a generalized formulation, without approximations, applicable to all material bodies from particle physics to cosmology. We are currently working on a unification of force fields based entirely on PG principles (Danilatos, 2024). We introduced the concepts of black-mass and hyle without attempting to constrain PG into and by existing, possibly failed, theories. Fatio’s idea has been (a) either applied in a Newtonian only approximation by and large, or (b) completely sidelined by mainstream physics for too long, in both cases without ever bringing it to its logical conclusion. We attempt to rectify all this by exploring the “what if” possibility about PG theory. The wider scientific community can contribute towards this goal.

Newton’s gravitational law contains mass and G , neither of which represent an actual physical property or entity. Mass is proportional to an amount of hyle but only in ordinary bodies of low density (Newtonian regime), but deviates greatly with increase of density. The universal constant of G then is an artificial factor with no direct physical significance either. They are both redundant in deriving the force under PG, whilst they have become the basis or starting point in the development of prevailing theories.

Again, on the key issue of mass, Denisov & Logunov (1982) state that: *“It is shown that the inertial mass introduced in the general theory of relativity depends on the choice of the three-dimensional coordinate system, so that it can take arbitrary values. This means that the inertial mass in Einstein’s theory is devoid of any physical meaning. In addition, the expression for the inertial mass in Einstein’s theory in the general case of an arbitrary three-dimensional coordinate system does not have a classical Newtonian limit, so that the general theory of relativity does not satisfy the principle of correspondence with Newton’s theory.”*

Mass has been a fundamental problem since Newton’s time. Physicists have vacillated about mass between the notion of “matter” and abstract mathematical formulations. We resort to gravions giving gravitational mass to hyle (real-mass). We can liken the gravions to a flying shuttle weaving a fabric out of yarn: Gravions weave the fabric of effective mass out of hyle. The material form of objects as we experience them is created from an amorphous substrate/matter (hyle) through the action of gravions and other push particles by staged processes waiting to be specified. We would need to bring together all particle physics data to date and attempt to explain them by PG. We need to map the available data on the PG framework.

One important corollary here is to indicate that the current scales of the cosmos may require adjustment. This should not be overlooked even if some specific mechanisms above might turn out to be fallacious simplifications. Therefore, prospective criticisms against PG may themselves be based on false grounds. In turn, agreement or not by various theories (including GR) involving existing measurements on dwarfs, neutron stars and black holes will have to be revised. As a result, the findings of PG, like the novel relationship between mass and force, should not be dismissed on the basis of some other theory until an integrated resolution of all emerging issues is obtained.

It is quite plausible that we have grasped the key to solving many outstanding issues and paradoxes in current physics. The notion of an expanding universe and the Big Bang theory can be artifacts both from incorrect measurements and from adhering to incorrect principles and theoretical tenets for too long.

For a deeper appreciation of our proposals, we quote from Feyerabend (2010): *“The consistency condition which demands that new hypotheses agree with accepted theories is unreasonable because it preserves the older theory, and not the better theory. Hypotheses contradicting well-confirmed theories give us evidence that cannot be obtained in any other way. Proliferation of theories is beneficial for science, while uniformity impairs its critical power. Uniformity also endangers the free development of the individual”*.

In relation to our method, it is further pertinent to quote again from Feyerabend (2010): *“No theory ever agrees with all the facts in its domain, yet it is not always the theory that is to blame. Facts are constituted by older ideologies, and a clash between facts and theories may be proof of progress. It is also a first step in our attempt to find the principles implicit in familiar observational notions”*.

Note: If PG ultimately proves to be a valid theory, which of necessity must replace all related faulty ones currently in use, a large amount of work would be required by the scientific community across many fields. The prospect of this requirement may now deter scientists from wanting to deal with PG. However, the cost of continuing worldwide expensive projects based on false premises would be orders of magnitude higher than the relatively minuscule cost of at least an initial investigation into PG. The consequences would become even worse in the existing knowledge of this possibility.

5.2 Expanding universe under PG

An expanding universe is not incompatible with push gravity. If, after taking into consideration the proposed revision of astronomical and astrophysical measurements, we still find that the universe is expanding, then

our theory is capable of explaining it too. We may still have to resort to a kind of Big Bang, which could also be accommodated by our PG theory. In fact, we have produced one possible explanation of a universe expanding under PG from the outset of the theory with a section devoted to it. We copy an excerpt below:

The idea of push gravity occurred to this author during work on gas flows in an environmental scanning electron microscope (ESEM) (Danilatos, 1997) using the direct simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) method (Bird, 1995). The latter method made possible the study of gaseous flows under specific conditions (e.g. novel differential pumping stages by Danilatos (2012)). It was tested and confirmed the idea of two spherical bodies being “attracted” to each other, when the mean free path (m.f.p.) of gaseous molecules was much greater than the diameter of the spheres, while absorption to any degree was also present. It was then thought that the same might happen, if planets and stars are immersed in a medium with particles having mean free paths much greater than the size of the celestial bodies. That would then be the cause of gravitational acceleration and force to start with. For distances much greater than the m.f.p., no “attraction” force is generated, while the celestial bodies will float around and more:

The implication of this would go much further, if we consider an analogy between a real (familiar) gas and the universe gas (or gravion gas), as follows: Dust particles in a real gas under the above condition of m.f.p. would appear to attract each other (at close range), while also, if the overall gas is set free to expand, the dust particles would expand in unison with the surrounding gas. Likewise, the stars, planets and celestial bodies are like dust particles attracting each other at relatively short distances (relative to m.f.p.), but move apart from each other as a whole, when the distances become far greater than the m.f.p. of the gravions behaving like an expanding gas. We may then say that PG is consistent with an expanding universe and consistent with the conclusions of the theory of a big bounce or bang, but not with existing theories based on different premises. The visual picture of a starry night through a high resolution telescope conveys the impression of a dusty space, which might be more than a coincidence to treat it like an expanding dusty gas. In proposing such a model, the observed accelerated expansion rate of the universe might correspond to the initial (or close to it) accelerated rate of expansion of a gas, which, however, eventually reaches supersonic and hypersonic speeds, after which it expands at a constant rate (with terminology taken from the dynamics of an expanding gas, as through an aperture). The initial gaseous expansion may be taken like the inflation period of current Big Bang theories (and vice-versa). Therefore, if this model is correct, our universe exists still at an initial (or near initial) expanding rate state, provided that the proposed revision of existing measurements still indicate an accelerated expansion. Finally, if this model were to be accepted, dark energy (repulsion) of current theories might have a tangible explanation via PG too. Terminology is again important to avoid confusion. If the expanding gravion gas is responsible for pushing galaxies apart (not “attracting” them), then we might as well call this type of field “negative push gravity” (NPG), consistent with “dark energy”.

None of the above should be less plausible than various other hypotheses already on record to explain the observed expanding rate of the universe, like: A dark energy inherent in the fabric of space itself, or the quintessence field that expands space at changing rates, or a phantom energy and so on and so forth. In any event, the said applications of PG in this area are only on a tentative basis, which should be adjusted as new data and information are compiled on any of these controversial topics.

In an overall conclusion, while PG started as an alternative explanation of gravity, it has been developed to a stage providing overwhelming evidence that it also constitutes a greater framework to explain particle physics and cosmology. It may have ushered the New Physics that is being discussed and expected worldwide. Clearly, this makes it a major research area to be served well above and beyond one individual. The participation of the wider scientific community is imperative, if to accelerate science forward within the near future and not another century later.

Appendix

We provide a summary of the derivation of mass and force between two spherical material bodies in an abbreviated form extracted from Danilatos (2024).

For a single and lone sphere sufficiently away (at $r = \infty$) from the influence by any other bodies, we symbolize its mass, be it “intrinsic”, “rest”, “gravitational” or “effective” by m_e (per PG) as in the following expressions:

$$m_{intrinsic} \equiv m_{rest} = m_e \equiv m_{e\infty} \equiv m_e(\infty) \quad (16)$$

and is given by:

$$m_e = \frac{\pi}{\Lambda_{PG}} A_R R^2 = \frac{g_0}{G} A_R R^2 \quad (17)$$

whereas at a distance r from another sphere with effective mass $M_e \equiv M_e(\infty)$, the corresponding masses become:

$$m_{er} \equiv m_e(r) < m_e \quad \text{and} \quad M_{er} \equiv M_e(r) < M_e \quad (18)$$

The above effective masses vary with distance and are given by PG equations via multiple integration of all gravions penetrating and absorbed the two spheres. We have established two equivalent methods for finding the same mass. The first method involves integration of a function $m_V(r)$ over the bulk (volume) of each sphere, while the second method involves integration of another function $m_S(r)$ over the surface of each sphere. Both methods yield identical results for the mass:

$$m_e(r) = \iiint_V m_V(r) dV = \iint_S m_S(r) dS \quad (19)$$

The exact functions, variables of integration and number of integrals are provided in the Appendix of the main report on PG.

Correspondingly for the force $F_{PG}(r)$, we have found by PG means, i.e. by integration of all gravion absorption from all directions that

$$F_{PG}(r) = \iiint_V f_V(r) dV = \iint_S f_S(r) dS \quad (20)$$

where $f_V(r)$ and $f_S(r)$ are corresponding force functions to be integrated over the bulk (volume), or the surface of the same spheres.

We have found that Newton's gravitational law for the force $F_N(r)$ is given by:

$$F_N(r) = G \frac{m_e(\infty)M_e(\infty)}{r^2} > G \frac{m_e(r)M_e(r)}{r^2} \quad (21)$$

This involves only the "intrinsic" masses (infinitely apart from each other) and not the actual effective masses at the given distance!

Then, we have further found that:

$$F_{PG}(r) = F_N(r) \quad (22)$$

The above finding is both novel and important. Firstly, it reveals that the force can be found without resorting to the quantities of "mass" and to the universal gravitational constant G , both of which were empirically introduced by Newton. We do not need them in the first place, in order to find the force. Secondly, it reveals that the correct "masses" in Newton do not exist at the given distance, but they existed when the two spheres were very far apart as to not influence each other. Thus, Newton fortuitously used a parameter (of mass) that is created by the gravion absorption in the "lone" state of each sphere separately. Thirdly, the above finding of ours is valid not only for Newtonian bodies of very low density (ordinary objects) but for any density of bodies all the way up to black holes.

Given Eq. 22, we can write three equations in a configuration:

$$G \frac{m_e(\infty)M_e(\infty)}{r^2} \stackrel{1}{=} \iiint_V f_V(r) dV \stackrel{2}{=} \iint_S f_S(r) dS \stackrel{3}{=} G \frac{m_e(\infty)M_e(\infty)}{r^2} \quad (23)$$

whereby equations $\stackrel{1}{=}$, $\stackrel{2}{=}$ and $\stackrel{3}{=}$ constitute three interrelated theorems that have been confirmed, so far, by numerical integration of the involved integrals. The precision of integration was up to 9 decimal places limited only by the computer integrator used. It was tested for several cases covering a wide range of densities, which indicates the veracity of our conclusion. Much higher precision would be required for Newtonian bodies, but bodies with high density are covered within the precision of integration used. The Python codes employed have been published in Danilatos (2023) with more information given also in the Appendix of Danilatos (2024).

Regarding the associated energy relations in PG, we should note that they involve the exchange and variation of energy and mass not only between the above two two spheres but, in addition, between the spheres (or a system of bodies) and the surrounding flux intensity J_0 . The exchange of mass should not be alarming to the conventional reader, because this takes place at the sub-"fundamental"-particle level and does not involve transfer of materials at the atomic/molecular level. After all, we have explained that "mass" is an energy rate parameter and not "matter", or ordinary stuff. The mass Eq. 19 computes the absorption of gravions from the surrounding space. The conventional potential energy $U_N(r)$, the PG potential energy $U_{PG}(r)$ and the

work defined by $\int F(r)dr$ are only components in the total energy balance between the open thermodynamic system of bodies and the gravion medium; they are inadequate by themselves (individually) to account for phenomena in cosmology. For Newtonian bodies, PG reduces to conventional quantitative relationships, but for dense/large bodies (like white dwarfs, neutron stars, black holes, etc.), PG overtakes classical mechanics. Now, our own $E_e = m_e c^2$ in PG prevails universally in every case for each part of the system and for the total system for all types of bodies. This means that we have emission or absorption of energy in gravity, when the spheres vary their distance in a similar fashion as we have emission/absorption of electromagnetic energy in electricity between charges (= electrical effective masses) as described in push electricity (PE) by Danilatos (2024): The gravitational energy exchange (emission/absorption) escapes undetected in planetary or lesser ordinary material systems, whereas it appears as photons in electromagnetism involving dense sub-atomic particles. However, we should also expect to receive measurable gravitational energy from interacting large and dense celestial bodies.

We could not find an analytical expression for the mass in the output of integrals in Eqs. 19, which forced us to resort to numerical integration (conveniently used for the force as well). However, given Eq. 22, we expect an analytical expression out of the multiple integrals for the force in Eqs. 20. Hence, there should also be an analytical proof of the same theorems $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{2}{3}$ and $\frac{3}{4}$ in Eqs. 23. Further theoretical processing and analysis of all of the above derivations can be done separately. Such work has been deferred to allow this author to proceed with other mundane tasks of PG theory, while other workers are welcome to make a contribution to this and many other outstanding areas of the fledgling theory of PG.

Now, the variation of effective mass with distance between two bodies, i.e. a decrease of mass with decrease of distance, means that Newton’s gravitational law, if applied using the effective masses, yields a smaller value of force than if the masses were independent of distance as is assumed by Newton. PG finds exactly the latter, i.e. the force behaves as if the masses were invariant without actually being so! This is a novel understanding previously unexpected. It is a consequence of the underlying mathematical (better, physical) relationship among the PG parameters involved via the gravion absorption. In other words, the originally envisaged or assumed “amount of matter” (via mass, later also via intrinsic or rest mass) in gravitation turns out to be a mathematical parameter concurrently accompanied by a “universal” constant G , while both of these quantities depend on the gravion density flux in a given region of the universe. PG commits no sacrilege against “intrinsic mass”, which ultimately is not invariable or sacred. For example, if the same body changes shape the “intrinsic” mass would also change, a lesson at variance with Newtonian mechanics. Now, PG explains what “mass” is and provides exactly the greater framework, within which the long standing classical parameters have emerged.

Note: To those who may read with disbelief that shape alone and orientation with another body can affect the mass of a body with a fixed amount of matter, we reply that objects with planetary size are invariably close to spherical geometry, while we cannot remold them to a different shape and measure the variation of mass. We can reshape an ordinary size body, but the effective mass difference is expected to be so small as we cannot detect (measure) it with available equipment to date. In fact, this possibility depends on the prevailing value of g_0 , which we need to establish one way or another. Long interplanetary trajectories of bodies with non-spherical shapes may help on this question, like the Oumuamua anomaly (Bialy & Loeb, 2018) and other flyby effects by man-made spacecraft, which could be explained by a variable orientation of the primary axis of their non-spherical shape.

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